

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: UMEH****FIRST NAME: GREGORY****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 8)

THE ART OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The art of writing has evolved over the years, and the written word is a particular attribute of *Homo sapiens*. It is a unique way of recording, documenting, storing, and sharing information, which has endured for many years. The origin of written words is intricate and fractured, but history points to the Arabs and western civilizations as the pioneers of early writing, which has morphed over the years to its current complexities. In Nigeria and other African countries, south of the Sahara, the history of written words is much recent compared to Western, Middle-East and more advanced nations. We write for many reasons, and written word, unlike the oral tradition of communication has more useful value, touches more lives, can be stored for a more extended period and shared with a broader audience. The reason for written words could be education, communication, history, or personal. Knowledge without written words is incomplete, and human beings over time have improved on their written words, making communication more natural and seamless. Nigeria has made its mark in the literary world, producing the first Nobel Prize winner for Literature in 1986, but as a country, we are yet to achieve our full potential in literature.

The teaching and learning of English Language and grammar have suffered over the year, with underfunding of education, dysfunctional curriculum, lack of books and teaching aids and poor remuneration of teachers. The quality of researches and articles from Nigerian students has no doubt fallen, due mainly to inadequate funding and a declining standard of academic training at both undergraduate and graduate levels. The teaching of literature and necessary literal skills at the universities has dramatically decreased, and this is more acute at the post-graduate schools. The theses and dissertations from masters and doctorate students are full of avoidable spelling, grammatical, and

punctuation errors. The guidance and mentorship of graduate students in the course of their research have also declined. The interest in creative works and literature of an average Nigerian undergraduate and graduate student is shallow, and more attention paid to social media and other non-literally activities. The libraries in Nigerian Universities lack current journals, books, internet facilities, and motivated staff, making teaching and learning of literature very difficult. The students are impatient to complete their studies, and this can lead to malpractices, plagiarism, and fraud of all kinds.

Plagiarism is a grave offense and is rife in Nigerian universities, and has encouraged laziness among students and the teaching staff. Graduate students complete their programs without sound knowledge and foundation in academic writing and research methods. The academic curriculum at Euclid University is unique, as emphasis is on academic writing and development of sound literal skills. The academic cannot do without written words, and it is his or her key to a successful professional life. I treasure written words, and Master of Science in International Public Health (MIPH) at Euclid University is another step at deepening my love for academic writing.

2) ACADEMIC VERSUS NON-ACADEMIC WRITING

Academic writing comes with rules, guidelines, and styles, which are well explained in ACA-401 coursepack period one. The structures employed in academic writing allows for comparable assessment of scholarly works of scholars of diverse backgrounds and geography, for example, guidelines for essay writing, dissertation, thesis, journal article, though may vary from place to place, university to university, journal to journal are united by common elements. In creative writing, elements, like the theme, plot, point of view, diction, styles, and others feature prominently, but consensus on their application and use are as diverse as the number of creative writers on planet earth. Unlike academic writing, non-academic writing is more liberal, informal, individualistic, and personal in style, for examples, newspaper editorials, and columns, novels, etcetera.

The ACA-401 coursepack period one has properly x-rayed academic writing, revealing the structures, forms, and elements of an excellent paper, which graduate students must embrace for a successful Master of Science (MSc) program. I see myself making more progress in my academic life, by mastering these qualities of excellent writing, through constant revision and practice in the course of my sojourn at Euclid University. I have written an article for peer-reviewed journals, but coursepack period one has deepened my horizon of academic writing and brought to the fore the following fundamentals: necessary steps in writing an essay, “starting, researching and organizing your ideas,” “what is an excellent paper,” elements like, “plagiarism, citation, referencing,” styles, “American versus British English,” “rules of thumbs for writing papers,” literature 101 review, “important reminders,” Latin abbreviations and expressions and so forth (EUCLID 2015, 2). The ACA-401 coursepack has exposed me to the many ways of approaching academic writing, in forms and styles, for examples, citation and referencing, “American Psychological Association (APA) versus Chicago Manual of Styles (CMS)” or in spelling, “American versus British English” (EUCLID 2015, 66) and so forth. I am a student of both the APA and the CMS (Turabian), but more at home with the APA as my first MSc at

Makerere University, Kampala, was in clinical psychology, (hope you can understand the bias). The ACA-401 coursepack period one has also guided me on how to navigate these contrasts and opposites, and when and how to make use of one form or style over the other and so forth. The orientation provided by coursepack period one on academic writing will deepen my skills, interest, understanding, and practice of good literature, during and after my MIPH program at EUCLID.

3) SKILLS AND TIPS FOR EXCELLENT WRITING

I am more thrilled on the tips for excellent writing provided by the ACA-401 coursepack period one for MSc students, for examples, Questions, and Answers (Q&As); sample corrections to papers; styles, personal versus academic and so forth. The essential Q&As deal with common mistakes graduate students often make during writing; for example, the use of apostrophes in words that end with “s” when indicating possession. Other examples are “how many spaces go after a period?” “What is the proper use of “its” and “it’s”?” “What is the proper use of “your” and “you’re”?” “What is the difference between “that” and “which”?” etcetera (EUCLID 2015, 47). The sample corrections to paper provided useful tips on how to write a good essay: making use of the right word in an essay, how to develop an idea in an essay, when to apply a paragraph, when to end a sentence, how to begin a new sentence, how to link one sentence to the other and so on.

The review of Curriculum Vitae (CV) will no doubt help me in updating my CV, as it has useful tips on how to market your skills, competencies, and credentials to employers. (EUCLID 2015, 60). The coursepack period one provided useful tips on recognizing and handling the differences between American and British English on pronunciation, spelling, grammar, syntax, and general usage. The differences between American and British English are more manifest in terms or expression of words, creativity in the use of words, euphemistic references, vocabulary, political correctness, changing culture and so on (EUCLID 2015, 54). The skills that come from these tips are immeasurable, as academic life and its fulfilment depend on excellent writing skills. I have learned new Latin words, understood better many Latin words I knew before, and appreciates better the context in which they should be used for seamless communication.

4) CONCLUSION

I have enjoyed coursepack period one and what I found at the end exceeded my expectations, further confirming Euclid University as the best choice for MIPH “Nulli Secundus.” I am also convinced no graduate training is complete without excellence in ACA-401 coursepack period one. The forms, elements, skills, and styles in academic writing have roots in ACA-401 coursepack period one. I look forward to a fulfilling academic life at Euclid University and will build on the foundation of coursepack period one to accomplish my ambition and aspiration. The goal of excellence in academic life, hopefully will be realized at the end of my study. I am very grateful to those that put this coursepack together, the instructors, faculty staff and especially the International Faculty

Coordinator (IFC) (Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck), I can see his shadow in all the excellent package for my academic delight, despite his other numerous engagements.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period one. Retrieved from:
<http://www.EUCLIDuniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.